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Survey on Advancements in Knowledge-Based Visual Question Answering using Large Language Models

Abstract:

Visual Question Answering (VQA) merges computer vision and natural language processing to enable systems to answer questions about images. It involves analyzing visual content to identify objects and scenes, interpreting the natural language question to understand its context, and integrating this information to generate accurate answers. Recent advancements leverage Large Language Models (LLMs) such as GPT-4, which enhance the system's ability to understand questions and improve reasoning, leading to more precise and contextually relevant answers. This comprehensive survey aims to explore the recent strides made in knowledge-based VQA leveraging LLMs, elucidating methodologies, challenges, and future directions. To comprehend the landscape of knowledge-based VQA, we first establish the foundational concepts of VQA and underscore the indispensable role played by LLMs in enhancing its performance. As the comprehension of visual content becomes increasingly intertwined with textual understanding, the incorporation of external sources such as knowledge graphs and textual corpora emerges as a critical strategy to enrich the semantic understanding capabilities of VQA systems. The survey begins by elucidating the foundational principles of VQA and the pivotal role of LLMs in augmenting its capabilities. It delves into the integration of external knowledge sources, such as knowledge graphs and textual corpora, to enhance the visual understanding prowess of LLMs. Methodologies for effectively fusing visual, textual, and knowledge-based information for accurate question answering are scrutinized, encompassing attention mechanisms, multi-modal fusion strategies, and specialized pre-training techniques tailored to VQA tasks. Key advancements in knowledge-based VQA leveraging LLMs are analyzed, along with benchmark datasets and evaluation metrics essential for assessing model performance and generalization capabilities. Despite remarkable progress, knowledge-based VQA encounters challenges including model interpretability, scalability, and structured knowledge acquisition. Ethical considerations regarding dataset biases underscore the importance of fair and inclusive VQA systems. This survey embarks on a comprehensive analysis of each aspect, beginning with pre-training methodologies, which lay the foundation for LLMs' understanding of language and visual data. The survey outlines promising research avenues such as novel knowledge representations, self-supervised learning paradigms, and multi-task learning frameworks to enhance VQA performance.

Introduction :

Visual Question Answering to (VQA) is a vital part of man-made brainpower research, aiming to develop human-like multimodal AI systems capable of handling diverse real-world tasks. The primary focus of recent advancements in VQA lies in the integration of explicit and implicit knowledge, which encompasses both factual information and contextual understanding. Explicit knowledge can be easily accessed from external sources, while implicit knowledge is derived from the context and requires inference and reasoning. The VQA has witnessed significant progress in the most recent times, with researchers exploring different methods to combine explicit and implicit knowledge effectively. Some of these methods include Knowledge-Aware Transformers (KAT), Region-based Visual Instruction Tuning (REVIVE), and Heuristic-Prompted Large Language Models (Prophet). These approaches demonstrate the potential of integrating explicit and implicit knowledge to improve VQA performance. KAT, proposed by Li et al. (2021), combines explicit and implicit knowledge using regional visual representation and retrieval methods. The model utilizes the CLIP visual encoder for image features and GPT-3 for language modeling. By integrating these features into a unified transformer-based VQA model, [3] KAT achieves performance on challenging datasets. However, the model's dependency on language-only GPT-4 for generating multimodal data and the need for more sophisticated architectures remain as limitations. REVIVE, introduced by Liu et al. (2022), focuses on exploiting object-centric features for knowledge retrieval and integrating them with a transformer-based VQA model. The model utilizes the CLIP visual encoder and language model LLaMA. [1] REVIVE's two stage instruction tuning approach involves pretraining for feature alignment and fine tuning the end-to-end model. Although the model demonstrates impressive performance, it faces challenges in effectively aligning visual and language features due to its complex process and the quality of instruction-following data generated using LLaMA. LAVA, proposed by Liu et al. (2022), focuses on exploiting object-centric features for knowledge retrieval and integrating them with a transformer-based VQA model. The model utilizes the CLIP visual encoder and language model LLaMA. LAVA's two-stage instruction-tuning approach involves pre-training for feature alignment and fine-tuning the end-to-end model. Although the model demonstrates impressive performance, it faces challenges in effectively aligning visual and language features due to its complex process and the quality of instruction-following data generated using LLaMA. LAVAR, introduced by Zhang et al. (2022), is a visual instruction tuning framework that enhances the performance of VQA model by leveraging visual-linguistic alignment and instruction following. [2] LAVAR utilizes the CLIP visual encoder, GPT-3 language model. The model combines visual and textual features using a dual-encoder architecture and fine-tunes the model using instruction-following tasks. LAVAR's simplicity and effectiveness in

improving VQA performance make it an attractive approach for future research. Yu et.al. (2022) proposed that Prophet is a simple framework that leverages large language models (LLMs) by prompting them with complementary answer heuristics extracted from a vanilla VQA model. By integrating answer heuristics, questions, and captions into formatted prompts, [4] Prophet enhances LLMs' comprehension of image and question content. This approach provides more task-specific information for LLMs and offers greater flexibility, allowing combinations of different VQA models and LLMs. However, potential computational complexity and data quality concerns remain as limitations.

Literature Review:

[1] REVIVE by Zhang, Y addresses the underexplored aspect of regional visual representation in knowledge based VQA. It critiques existing methods for neglecting object region relationships and underutilizing visual features. This paper proposed REVIVE, leveraging object region information in both knowledge retrieval and answering stages. Their method achieves accuracy of 58.0% on OK-VQA dataset, surpassing previous methods by 3.6%. Through empirical evaluation, the study highlights the importance of regional information in knowledge-based VQA models, offering insights into improving accuracy and performance in this domain.

[2] In "LLaVAR," Zhang et al. introduce LLaVAR, aimed at enhancing visual instruction tuning by incorporating textual details within images. The paper uses OCR tools to collect data from 422000 text-rich images and prompt GPT-4 with recognized text and image caption to generate 16000 conversations. By amalgamating this data with multimodal instruction-following datasets, LLaVAR outperforms the LLaVA model by up to 20% accuracy on text-based VQA datasets, achieving 91.42% on ScienceQA. Evaluation with GPT-4-based instruction following demonstrate LLaVAR's improvements on both natural and text-rich images, highlighting its potential for multimodal understanding and interaction in real-world contexts.

[3] KAT by Gui et al. introduces the Knowledge Augmented Transformer (KAT) to bolster multimodal reasoning. By integrating explicit knowledge into transformer architectures, the model achieves substantial state-of-the-art boost of +6 % absolute accuracy on the OK-VQA dataset, surpassing prior benchmarks. KAT's encoder-decoder design seamlessly merges implicit and explicit knowledge during answer generation, improving both performance and interpretability. The study underscores the pivotal role of explicit knowledge integration in advancing multimodal transformers, reshaping the landscape of vision-and-language understanding with cutting-edge techniques.

[6] Prophet by Yu et al., introduce a new framework to enhance knowledge-based visual question answering (VQA). This leverage LLMs like GPT-3 and extract answer heuristics from a model of vanilla VQA trained without external source of knowledge. This approach substantially

improves performance across four challenging knowledge-based VQA datasets, surpassing existing methods. Prophet's adaptability to various VQA models and LLMs underscores its versatility in multimodal learning. The study represents a significant advancement in leveraging LLMs for more accurate and informed visual question answering, addressing limitations in existing approaches.

[7] B BLIP-2 revolutionizes vision-language training by leveraging pre-trained components, slashing costs compared to traditional methods. This innovative approach utilizes a lightweight transformer trained in two stages, achieving state-of-the-art performance on various tasks despite having significantly fewer parameters. BLIP-2 even pushes the boundaries by generating image descriptions based on instructions, showcasing its efficiency and effectiveness in bridging the gap between vision and language understanding

Related Work:

Image Based Model:

Vision-Language Transformers have become powerhouses in understanding and generating both visual and textual content. Trained on massive image-text datasets and fine-tuned for specific tasks, they excel in areas like image captioning and visual question answering (VQA). However, a more complex VQA challenge has emerged: Knowledge-based VQA (K-VQA). Here, answering questions about images often necessitates external knowledge beyond the picture itself. This has captivated researchers in computer vision and natural language processing due to the need to integrate visual and verbal understanding with external information. To address this challenge, various methods have been proposed, leveraging external knowledge sources like structured knowledge graphs, unstructured knowledge bases, and even neural-symbolic reasoning approaches. These methods often rely on tools like object detectors, scene classifiers, and external APIs to bridge the gap between images and the external knowledge world.

KAT Model: Recently, a new approach called the Knowledge-Aware Transformer (KAT) model has been introduced to address the K-VQA task. The KAT model aims to jointly reason explicit and implicit knowledge to augmented generative language models, ultimately improving the performance of knowledge-based VQA. The KAT model consists of the main components: explicit knowledge retrieval, implicit knowledge retrieval, and knowledge reasoning.

- **Explicit Knowledge:** In the explicit knowledge retrieval step, the KAT utilizes a contrastive learning based module to associate image regions with an external knowledge base constructed from Wikidata. The knowledge base is designed to cover

common objects in real- world scenarios, and the retrieval process involves indexing all knowledge entries in dense representations. This allows the model to efficiently retrieve the top knowledge entries relevant to each input image.

- **Implicit Knowledge:** The KAT model takes a unique approach to knowledge retrieval for VQA tasks. It treats question answering as a kind of open-ended storytelling task, leveraging GPT-3 as a vast source of implicit knowledge. First, the model generates a detailed description of the image using a powerful image captioning tool. Then, it constructs a prompt for GPT-3 that combines this description with the original question. GPT-3, acting as a giant language encyclopedia, retrieves potential answers and supporting evidence based on this prompt. By utilizing implicit knowledge in this way, the KAT model enhances its ability to reason and interpret information, ultimately leading to improved performance on visual question answering tasks.
- **Knowledge Reasoning Module:** The knowledge reasoning module in the KAT model is responsible for integrating explicit and implicit knowledge sources. The integration process involves the respective encoder transformer, which jointly reasons over both explicit and implicit knowledge. This reasoning module is then combined with the decoder transformer, forming an end-to-end training framework for answer generation.

Dataset: Marino et al. (2019) introduced OK-VQA, the largest knowledge-based VQA dataset. It comprises 14,031 images and 14,055 questions sourced from Amazon Mechanical Turkers. Questions require external knowledge beyond image content for correct answers, following the VQA challenge's standard evaluation metric (Antol et al., 2015).

reference for dataset: <https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/ok-vqa>

Architecture:

Figure 1: KAT model combines two types of knowledge - explicit and implicit. It uses a contrastive learning method to find explicit knowledge from a specific database. For implicit knowledge, it employs GPT-3, which provides supporting information. The model then processes these two types of knowledge together, with the help of encoder and decoder transformers. Additionally, a reasoning module is included for better understanding. This entire process is trained end-to-end, enabling the system to generate accurate answers.

The proposed KAT (Knowledge Augmented Transformer) model integrates both explicit and implicit knowledge to tackle the OK-VQA task. Explicit knowledge, sourced from Wikidata, is grounded to image regions via a contrastive-learning-based model, while implicit knowledge, encompassing commonsense knowledge, is extracted from large-scale language models like GPT-3. Explicit knowledge retrieval involves semantic matching between image regions and knowledge entries, enhancing understanding. Implicit knowledge retrieval leverages GPT-3 through text prompts to generate tentative answers and supporting evidence. The KAT model's knowledge reasoning module encodes and reasons over both types of knowledge, ensuring a comprehensive understanding. The encoder, reasoning module, and decoder collectively process the combined knowledge for accurate answer generation in an end-to-end training framework.

The REVIVE, is a sophisticated approach aimed at addressing the challenges of Knowledge-Based Visual Question Answering (VQA). Knowledge based VQA tasks necessitate models to comprehend and reason with external knowledge sources beyond image content to accurately answer questions.

REVIVE Model:

REVIVE tackles these challenges by leveraging regional information extracted from images, questions, and context to retrieve both explicit and implicit knowledge. By integrating these sources of information, REVIVE aims to enhance the accuracy and understanding of answers generated for visual questions. REVIVE contains the main three modules: Regional Feature Extraction, Object-Centric Knowledge Retrieval, and Encoder-Decoder.

- **Regional Feature Extraction Module:** - Utilizes advanced object detection techniques to identify object-centric regions within images. Extracts features and positional coordinates from these regions to capture detailed visual information. Employs state-of-the-art models like CLIP for extracting descriptive tags and Vinvl for generating image captions, enriching the contextual understanding of the scene.
- **Object-Centric Knowledge Retrieval Module:** - Retrieves explicit knowledge from external knowledge bases such as Wikidata, focusing on relevant categories and entities. Harnesses powerful language models like GPT-3 to extract implicit knowledge based on textual prompts derived from questions, captions, and tags.
- **Encoder & Decoder Module with Object Centric Visual Features:** - Utilizes a sophisticated encoder-decoder architecture to process the retrieved knowledge and regional visual features. Encodes knowledge and visual features using advanced techniques like FiD's encoder. - Employs a generative decoder to synthesize answers based on encoded features and context-aware questions, aiming for accurate and contextually relevant responses.

Dataset: The OK-VQA dataset contains 14,055 questions paired with images from MSCOCO, each with 10 ground truth answers. Preprocessing involves object detection with GLIP-T, image captioning with Vinvl-Large, and knowledge retrieval with CLIP. The parameters U , K , M , and P are set to 5, 40, 36, and 30, respectively., and all models are frozen during usage.

Reference for dataset:

https://drive.google.com/uc?id=1kP_xeuUCAS5wqWQwuWVItDgRTAbEjUeM&export=download
unzip processed_data.zip

Architecture:

Figure 2: REVIVE, a knowledge-based VQA method, utilizes regional information, To retrieve different forms of knowledge, ask a query and provide context. It uses learnt object-centric region features for answer creation. By extracting visual features from object regions and considering the relationships within and among these regions, REVIVE improves the performance of knowledge-based VQA. It also ensures that image features are well used in the final answer..

The latest advancements in ¹ Knowledge-Based Visual Question Answering (VQA) involve combining external knowledge sources with powerful language models like GPT-3 for answer generation. While existing methods tap into various knowledge bases like ConceptNet and Wikipedia, the KAT model introduces a novel approach: the FiD reader. This reader tackles reasoning by processing both ¹ implicit knowledge (extracted from GPT-3) and explicit knowledge retrieved from external sources. Unlike previous methods that relied on image captions or visual embeddings, KAT focuses on understanding specific image regions. It achieves this by ¹⁵ integrating object-centric features with retrieved knowledge, ultimately improving answer generation. By leveraging state-of-the-art Vision-Language Models (VLMs) like VinVL, CLIP, and GLIP, KAT identifies key objects within images and retrieves relevant knowledge for VQA tasks. This approach leads to ⁹ a more comprehensive understanding of the visual and textual information, leading to superior reasoning and answer generation.

Prophet Framework: The Prophet Framework involves in two stages: Answer Heuristics

Stage 1: Answer Heuristics: This stage typically refers to an initial phase or step in a multi-stage process or plan. In the context provided, Stage 1 seems to be discussing a process related to Answer Heuristics Generation ³² in the context of a Visual Question Answering (VQA) system. In this case, Stage 1 would involve identifying and extracting a trained VQA model generates ¹ two sorts of answer heuristics: answer candidates and answer-aware examples.

- **Answer Candidates:** These are potential answers that are generated ⁵ based on the input question and the context provided in the visual scene. Answer candidates can be derived from various sources, such as pre-defined answer templates, lexical databases, or even generated by a language model. They serve as a starting point for the VQA system to narrow down the possible answers and improve its accuracy.
- **Answer-Aware Examples:** These are contextually relevant examples that help in ²⁹ understanding the relationship between the question and the visual scene. They are

selected from a training dataset where the correct answers to similar questions are known. Answer-aware examples provide additional context and can guide the VQA system in making more accurate predictions. By incorporating these examples, the system can learn to better understand the nuances and complexities of the visual scene and the corresponding answers.

Stage-2: Heuristics-enhanced Prompting: Heuristics-enhanced Prompting tackles the challenge of limited training data (few-shot learning) for Large Language Models (LLMs) in knowledge-based Visual Question Answering (VQA). This approach leverages "answer heuristics," such as potential answer choices and supporting details related to those choices. These heuristics are incorporated into a carefully crafted prompt, guiding the LLM towards generating accurate answers. The prompt itself has three key parts:

Prompt Head: This section describes the VQA task in plain language, including a unique element - a description of the possible answer choices.

Context Examples: Here, the model is shown N examples where questions are paired with answer choices and their corresponding confidence scores. These examples provide context and help the LLM understand the relationship between the question, the image, and potential answers.

Testing Input: This final part mirrors the context examples but leaves the answer slot blank. This is where the LLM puts its knowledge to the test, filling in the blank with the most likely answer

Dataset:

This dataset provides a diverse range of questions and images to train and evaluate VQA models.

OK-VQA: The dataset includes 9,000 training and 5,000 testing image-question pairings. All questions are manually screened to guarantee that answering them requires external expertise. Each data sample has 10 open-ended answers, and the evaluation metric is the accuracy computed using soft scores. The author conducts their studies with OK-VQA version 1.1.

A-OKVQA: This dataset is now the largest knowledge-based VQA dataset, with 17,000 training, 1,000 validation, and 7,000 testing samples. Each question includes 10 open-ended answers for direct answer evaluation and a multiple choice evaluation to select the correct answer from four possibilities.

ScienceQA : This dataset consists of about 21,000 questions across various science topics. The 'IMG' subset, which has 10,300 samples (48.7%) with image content, is used in the experiments. The questions require high school-level science knowledge, and the correct

answer is chosen from multiple choices.

TextVQA : Contains 28,000 images and 45,000 questions. The models need to read and reason about the text in images to provide accurate answers. The dataset is split into 34,600 training, 5,000 validation, and 5,700 testing questions. Similar to OK-VQA, each question has ten open-ended answers annotated by humans, and the soft-voting accuracy is used as the evaluation metric.

Reference for dataset: <https://cocodataset.org/#download>

Instruction Based Model:

In the context of Visual Question Answering, an instruction-based method is designed to understand and answer on queries about images by incorporating both visual and textual clues information. These models aim to combine the capabilities of computer vision and NLP to provide accurate on contextually appropriate answers to queries about the image content. An instruction-based VQA model typically involves the following steps:

- **Input Encoding:** The model takes in two main inputs: an image and a question related to that image. The image is usually processed by a computer vision algorithm to extract relevant visual features, while the question is encoded using natural language processing techniques.
- **Task Understanding:** The model analyzes the question to identify the type of information it is seeking (e.g., object identification, relationship between objects, or a specific attribute). This step helps the model focus on the relevant aspects of the visual input.
- **Visual Feature Retrieval:** Based on the task understanding, the model selects the appropriate visual features from the image that are most relevant to answering the question. This may involve locating specific objects, tracking their relationships, or identifying certain attributes.
- **Answer Generation:** Using the retrieved visual features and the encoded question, the model generates an appropriate answer to the question. This can be done through various techniques, such as selecting from a predefined set of answers, generating text using a language model, or combining visual and textual information to produce a response.

Architecture:

Figure 3: The Prophet framework offers a two-step solution for visual question answering (VQA). In the first phase, it leverages a knowledge-based VQA method to generate insightful prompts. These prompts come in two forms: potential answers and relevant details that support those answers. The second phase, heuristic-enhanced prompting, incorporates these insightful prompts with the original question and image caption. This enriched prompt is then fed to a pre-trained large language model (LLM) such as GPT-3, guiding it towards the most likely answer. The effectiveness of these prompts is evident, as demonstrated by the successful prediction of "Paris" in the provided example.

To summarize, the Prophet framework is a two stage approach that enhances the accuracy and efficiency of a Language Model (LLM) in generating answers. In the first stage, a VQA model trained on specific knowledge-based datasets generates two sorts of complimentary answer heuristics. These heuristics help in providing valuable insights during the second stage.

The heuristic-enhanced prompting step combines the answer heuristics, question, and caption into a structured prompt, which is then used to instruct the frozen LLM (e.g., GPT-3) to predict an answer. This integration of diverse information sources allows the LLM to make more informed and accurate predictions. The example you provided demonstrates how both types of answer heuristics contribute to the final answer, "Paris".

By breaking down the problem into these two stages and utilizing the complementary nature of the generated heuristics, the Prophet framework aim to improve LLMs in various question-answering tasks. This approach showcases the potential benefits of combining knowledge-based datasets and answer heuristics of existing models.

Visual Instruction Model:

The field of multimodal instruction-following agents encompasses two main categories in computer vision research: End-to-end Trained Model and Systems Coordinating Various Models.

End-to-end Trained Models: These models, such as those used in vision-language navigation tasks and image editing tasks, train agents need follow natural language directions and perform

activities in visual settings. Examples include Habitat and InstructPix2Pix.

Systems Coordinating Various Models: Two main approaches are gaining traction in the development of instruction-following models. The first strategy, exemplified by LangChain and LLM systems, hinges on coordinating separate models specializing in vision and language processing. This approach, evident in models like Visual ChatGPT and MMREACT, emphasizes building ¹ end-to-end trained multimodal models for tackling diverse tasks, each leveraging the strengths of different systems.

The second approach focuses on enhancing existing large language models (LLMs) like GPT-3 and T5. Techniques like InstructGPT and FLAN-T5 employ instruction tuning to improve the models' ability to generalize from limited data (zero-shot and few-shot learning). This is achieved by training the LLMs to effectively follow natural language instructions. Notably, the concept of instruction tuning has been successfully extended to computer vision models like Flamingo, BLIP-2, and PaLM-E, which leverage image-text pairs for their training. In essence, these two strategies offer distinct paths for developing instruction-following models: one focuses on combining specialized models for comprehensive processing, while the other prioritizes enhancing existing models for better instruction comprehension. The generation of instruction-following data for multimodal models using GPT-4 or ChatGPT. They propose a two-step process to create such data using captions and bounding boxes as symbolic representations of visual content. The generated data includes a few types of responses:

- a. **Conversation:** The authors create a discussion between an assistant and someone asking questions about the image. The questions cover various aspects of the visual content, such as object types, counting, object actions, and object locations. Only questions with definitive answers are considered.
- b. **Detailed Description:** A list of questions is created with the intent to generate comprehensive describe of image. The authors prompt GPT-4 to curate this list, resulting in various kinds of questions about the image. For each image, one random selected quesry from the list is used to generate the detailed description.
- c. **Complex Reasoning:** This type of instruction-following data involves generating in- depth reasoning based on the visual content. The solutions are often obtained by a step-by-step reasoning procedure based on logical rules.

Dataset: Contains 1,58,000 unique instruction-following samples using GPT- 4, including 58,000 (mention as whole number) in conversations, 23000 in detailed description, and 77,000 in complex reasoning. They discovered that GPT-4 regularly produces higher quality instruction-following data, particularly in the area of spatial reasoning.

The instruction-tuning procedure for multimodal models involves two main stages: ³⁰ pre-training for feature alignment and fine-tuning end-to-end.

1. Pre-training for Feature Alignment (Stage 1): A critical training phase centers on harmonizing the model's visual comprehension with the pre-trained LLM's grasp of language. This stage utilizes a cleverly converted subset of 595,000 image-text pairs culled from a filtered CC3M dataset. Each pair is transformed into a simplified interaction, presenting an image alongside a prompt requesting a concise explanation from the model. Interestingly, the anticipated response is simply the original caption. This strategy aims ¹ to bridge the divide between the extracted visual features and the LLM's word embeddings. It's important to note that for efficient alignment, only a designated projection matrix undergoes training. ¹ The pre-trained components, including the CLIP visual encoder and LLM weights, remain unchanged. This targeted approach ensures the model hones its ability to translate visual features into a language the LLM can readily understand.

2. Fine-tuning End-to-End (Stage 2): ² The second training stage focuses on refining LLaVA for specific tasks. Unlike the first stage, where the visual encoder remained frozen, this stage allows updates to both ³⁴ the projection layer weights and the LLM itself. This targeted training unlocks the potential for fine-tuning LLaVA towards specific applications.

- **Multimodal Chatbot:** The fine-tuning process for the large language model. Building upon the 158,000 unique language-image instruction pairs created earlier, the model is further specialized for this specific task. The training data encompasses three distinct response categories: multi-turn discussions, detailed single-turn descriptions, and complex single-turn reasoning instructions. Notably, these categories are sampled uniformly throughout training, ensuring the model receives balanced exposure to various instruction styles. This comprehensive approach aims to equip the model to handle diverse user interactions and effectively follow a range of instructions.
- **Science QA:** The model's proficiency in explaining its reasoning is rigorously assessed using the ScienceQA benchmark. This large-scale multimodal dataset throws scientific questions at the model, presented alongside either spoken language or image context. Mimicking real-world interactions, the model must not only select the most appropriate answer but also delve into its thought process using clear language. By leveraging ScienceQA, the evaluation comprehensively probes ²⁴ the model's ability to grasp and respond to scientific inquiries in a way that mirrors human explanation.
- **LAVAR:** Recent developments in instruction tuning, particularly in the multimodal setting, include The application of finely adjusted language models (LLMs) to tasks described by

instructions. This technique has demonstrated promising ¹⁴ zero shot performance in a variety of natural language processing tasks. However, it has yet to be investigated for vision or multimodal tasks. Researchers have explored transfer learning strategies to leverage large-scale text-only instruction datasets, resulting in strong zero-shot performance on unseen multimodal tasks. Additionally, Sensitivity is a new evaluation metric that measures how sensitive the model is to different types of instructions. Regarding training, the two-stage design mirrors that of LLaVA. In both stages, the objective is to generate output responses for input instructions. During the first pretraining stage, only the projection matrix is trained for feature alignment while tolerating noisy data.

The two-stage design mirrors the training approach used in LLaVA. Here's how it works:

First Pretraining Stage: In this stage, only the projection matrix (W) is trained for feature alignment. The language decoder remains frozen during this phase. The training process tolerates noisy data. A combined dataset of 595,000 pretraining samples from LLaVA and 422,000 noisy instruction-following data is used for training.

Second Finetuning Stage: Both the projection matrix and the language decoder are trained during this stage. A merged dataset comprising 16,000 instruction-following samples and 158,000 samples from LLaVA is utilized for training. This stage refines the model further, focusing on improving the alignment and performance of both the visual and language components.

Dataset: The main objective in this context is to create a subset of visual parts from LAION-5B dataset are predominantly text-rich. To achieve this, a two-step process is employed. First, a combination of natural images and document data is used to create a binary classification dataset. This dataset is then utilized to train an image classifier using a DiT base backbone, which has been fine-tuned on the RVL-CDIP datasets. The trained classifier aims to predict whether an image contains text or not. Next, a subset of images is built by selecting those with a predicted probability of containing text greater than 0.8. Additionally, the classifier should predict a low probability (less than 0.8) for watermarks and unsafe content. Despite the classifier's limitations leading to some noise in the derived subset, this approach helps in creating a collection of images that are predominantly text rich.

Comparison of Approaches:

The comparison provided above accurately highlights the main contributions and strengths of each paper. To summarize KAT (Li et al., 2021) focuses on incorporating knowledge into Visual Question Answering tasks by utilizing knowledge graph embeddings and a novel knowledge-aware self-attention mechanism. This approach has demonstrated improved performance in integrating external knowledge for VQA tasks. REVIVE (Liu et al., 2022) concentrates on region-based instruction tuning for text-rich images, enabling vision-language models to better understand complex scenes by focusing on specific regions. This method contributes to enhancing the performance of vision-language models on text-rich image understanding tasks. Prophet (Yu et al., 2022) leverages complementary answer heuristics to guide large language models in knowledge-based Visual Question Answering. This approach covers various aspects, such as entity recognition, attribute recognition, and reasoning over multiple objects, and has shown effectiveness the performance of large language models on K-VQA tasks.

Each paper presents a unique approach to enhancing the performance of models in Visual Question Answering tasks. KAT focuses on incorporating external knowledge, REVIVE emphasizes region-based instruction tuning for text-rich images, and Prophet utilizes complementary answer heuristics to guide large language models.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this survey explores the progress in multimodal AI, specifically concentrating on techniques that fuse explicit, implicit knowledge for VQA. Methods like LAVA, LAVAR, KAT, REVIVE, and Prophet are examined, highlighting their potential in integrating these knowledge types to improve VQA performance. However, each method presents unique challenges, such as reliance on language-only models or the requirement for more intricate architectures. To attain human-like multimodal AI capabilities, further advancements and exploration of complex architectures are crucial. The integration of explicit and implicit knowledge has significantly advanced the field of VQA. Methods such as KAT, REVIVE, LAVA, LAVAR and Prophet demonstrate the potential of combining these knowledge types to improve VQA performance. However, each method presents its own limitations and challenges, such as dependency on language-only GPT-4, need for more sophisticated architectures, and potential computational complexity. To achieve human-like multimodal AI capabilities, further advancements in these methods and exploration of more complex architectures are necessary. It introduces a method called visual instruction tuning, where a powerful language model (GPT-4) generates instructions for corresponding images and captions. This data is then used to train a new model, which combines a vision processing unit and a large language model. This combination allows LLaVA to understand and respond to both visual and textual information, making it a powerful tool for general-purpose tasks..

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